

PERIRENAL URINOMA IN A YOUNG WOMAN AFTER CHILDBIRTH.

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ABSTRACT

Urinoma is an accumulation of urine in the retroperitoneal area. It is caused by injuries to the kidneys, ureters, urinary bladder, or urethra. They may be confined, encapsulated fluid collections or may manifest as free fluid. Urine leaks have a variety of appearances.

This case describes a patient 27 years old, female presented at the emergency room with internal diseases with complaints of bloating and abdominal discomfort.

The history of the disease had begun three days before when she presented to the hospital with bloating that came increasing in quantity. She referred that five days ago gave birth to a child through transvaginal delivery. For the woman was the first birth of a child. According to the patient's own referral, her pregnancy was without problems but the birth lasted many hours.

There have been no previous health problems (confirmed by laboratory and imaging tests before pregnancy). There was a careful follow-up of the pregnancy. Except for an isolated case of a urinary tract infection, there was no other complication.

Further imaging revealed a large fluid in the pelvis and intraperitoneal. Treatment of this rare phenomenon is crucial for the delay in medical care can lead to abscess, hydronephrosis, electrolyte instability.

CT cystography and retrograde urethrographic are the diagnostic imaging studies of choice. In the appropriate setting, the use of these management options may reduce urinoma-related complications and limit or totally eliminate the need for urologic surgery.

Keywords: Urinoma, injuries, hydronephrosis, Childbirth

INTRODUCTION

Urinoma is an accumulation of urine in the retroperitoneal area. It is caused by injuries to the kidneys, ureters, urinary bladder or urethra. They may be confined, encapsulated fluid collections or may manifest as free fluid. Urine leaks have a variety of appearances. They may be misdiagnosed as ordinary ascites, abdominal or pelvic abscesses, hematomas, cystic masses, or pancreatic pseudo cysts. As urine extravasates into the retroperitoneal space, it can

cause a local inflammatory response on the surrounding perineal fat. This leads to lipolysis and an encapsulation of the urine, known as a urinoma. Bladder injuries occur due to blunt or penetrating trauma and are most commonly associated with pelvic fracture, but may also be iatrogenic. The likelihood of bladder injury and urine leakage is increased when the bladder is fully distended at the time of injury. There are two types of bladder injury: Extra peritoneal bladder injuries most often occurring

due to shearing or direct laceration of the bladder from pelvic fractures. Intraperitoneal bladder injuries generally result from blunt trauma which leads to a rapid rise in intraperitoneal pressure, causing the bladder dome to burst.

CASE REPORT

The patient S. V, 27 years old, presented at the emergency room of internal diseases with complaints of bloating and abdominal discomfort and tenderness. The history of the disease began three days before when she presented to the hospital with bloating that came increasing in quantity. She referred that five days ago gave birth to a child through transvaginal delivery. For her was the first birth of child. According to the patient's own referral, her pregnancy was without problems but the birth lasted many hours. There have been no previous health problems (confirmed by laboratory and imaging tests before pregnancy). There was a careful follow-up of the pregnancy. Except for an isolated case of a urinary tract infection, there was no other complication. On physical examination, the patient had tenderness to palpation specially to hypogastric area, and vital sign were normal. Ultrasonography showed presence of ascites. Results of the initial laboratory test were significant for uremia 107 mg / dl, creatinine 3.7 mg/dl and PCR 105 mg/ml.

The patient was hospitalized at the gastroenterology department on 10.02.2021 with the diagnosis of ascites. During her admission laboratory and imaging tests were performed. At the day of hospitalization, a urinary catheter was placed.

The results were as following: RBC 3.78×10^6 / mm³; Hgb 11.8 g / dl; Hct 38.5%; WBC 7.7×10^3 / mm³; PLT 443×10^3 / mm³; Glycemia 66 mg / dl, Urea 58 mg / dl; Total Bilirubin 0.89 mg / dl; Total Protein 5.5 g / dl; Albumin 2.8 mg / dl; ALT 12 U / L; AST 13 U / L; GGT 29 U / L; ALP 115 U / L; Amylase 31 U / L, PCR 20.85 mg / dl, Na 139 mmol / l; K 5.1 mmol / l, Creatinine clearance 228 ML / min, Creatine 1.13mg / dl; TSH 0.914 mU / L, FT3 1.6pg / ml, CEA 1ng / ml, CA-125 103.5 U / ml, Ferritin 211.90 ng / ml.

Ascitic fluid: 85% Neutrophils and 15%; Lymphocytes are seen on microscopic examination. No. of cells 570 mm³ cells / mm³; Glucose 51 mg / dl; Total Bilirubin 0.43mg / dl; Total Protein 1.5 mg / dl, Albumin 0.9mg / dl; LDH 868 U / L; Amylase 51 U / L; Cholesterol 23 mg / dl; Triglyceride 15 mg / dl.

Upper endoscopy: without lesions

She underwent a contrast computed tomography (CT), scan the abdomen and pelvis, which revealed free fluid in the Douglas pouch and intraperitoneal extravasation of intravenous contrast consistent with urinary bladder rupture (Fig 1).

Fig. 1. Axial computed tomography images showed free fluid in the Douglas pouch and intraperitoneal extravasation of intravenous contrast consistent with urinary bladder rupture.

Urinary bladder on retrograde contrast examination. Contrast exit is observed in the 'ceiling' of the bladder at '11-12' o'clock.

At first it was unnoticed because of the urinary catheter placed after birth. But when she was discharged home, the urine from the bladder flowed outside to the retroperitoneal cavity. In just a few days an enlarged abdomen was easily seen. In that moment the patient asked medical help. At first urea and creatinine levels were high. But when the patient was hospitalized in gastroenterology service, the placement of a urinary catheter made possible normalization of renal tests. The CT confirmed the diagnosis of bladder injury. The patient was transferred to the urology service where she receives conservative treatment and after a week left the hospital in good health conditions.

DISCUSSION

Urinoma is a rare and unique condition that refers to extravasation of urine from a disruption of the urinary collecting system at any level from the calix to the urethra. Clinically, patients can have symptoms ranging from being completely asymptomatic to an acute abdomen, hematuria, with vague malaise and pain being the most common. Urinomas are often small at presentation and

will reabsorb without intervention in most instances. In cases of a more significant injury, fever, urosepsis, or a larger urinoma that can be expanding and compressing or failing to reabsorb, a procedure is often necessitated by urology or interventional radiology to relieve the urinoma [1, 4]. Failure to do so can quickly lead to abscess, electrolyte imbalance, hydronephrosis, and urosepsis. First line treatment usually involves a drainage catheter placed into the urinoma, in addition to empiric antibiotics with the proper clinical signs and symptoms. Fluid culture is recommended to guide antibiotic treatment. Combined treatment with a suprapubic catheter and a transurethral bladder catheter may be required in cases of extra peritoneal bladder rupture with gross hematuria, especially if clots obstruct the transurethral bladder catheter within 48 hours of initial injury [2, 3]. when the catheter fails to drain the urinoma appropriately, a percutaneous nephrostomy tube may be placed to facilitate drainage often with a ureteral stent to promote healing [5]. Surgical reconstruction is reserving. Placing a transurethral bladder catheter explained the improvements in laboratory analysis to our patient (urea and creatinine improvements). After CT and drainage of liquid from the abdominal cavity, conservative treatment decided by urologists, was considered the best solution regarding in this case [4, 5]. The patient was discharged in good health conditions.

CONCLUSION

While urinomas are a rare entity, early awareness and prompt treatment are the basis for avoidance of more aggressive measures or even life-threatening complications in these patients. The good choice for diagnosis is CT, if uremia and creatine are normal, which help with the diagnosis. Conservative treatment versus drainage method is more superior to prevent the complications.

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REFERENCES

1. D. Basic, I. Ignjatovic, and M. Potic, "Iatrogenic ureteral trauma: A 16-year single tertiary centre experience," *Srpski Arhiv za Celokupno Lekarstvo*, vol. 143, no. 3-4, pp. 162-168, 2015.
2. B. Phillips, S. Holzmer, L. Turco et al., "Trauma to the bladder and ureter: a review of diagnosis, management, and prognosis," *European Journal of Trauma and Emergency Surgery*, vol. 43, no. 6, pp. 763-773, 2017.
3. E. K. Lang and L. Glorioso III, "Management of urinomas by percutaneous drainage procedures," *Radiologic Clinics of North America*, vol. 24, no. 4, pp. 551-559, 1986
4. J. B. McGeady and B. N. Breyer, "Current epidemiology of genitourinary trauma," *Urologic Clinics of North America*, vol. 40, no. 3, pp. 323-334, 2013.
5. L.A. Matthewus, E.M. Smith, and J.P. Spirnak, "Nonoperative treatment of major blunt renal lacerations with urinary extravasion," *The Journal of Urology*, vol.157, no 6, pp 2056-2058,1997.